

Fetal Memory, Prenatal Trauma, and Intergenerational Sexual Violence: A First-Person Narrative

Daniel Jimenez Batista

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-3538-5294>

Abstract

The article presents a first-person account of memories possibly formed during the gestational period, weaving together personal experience and scientific literature on fetal memory, prenatal music, maternal stress, and epigenetic programming. The narrator recounts a dream in which they perceive themselves within the maternal womb, linking it to an episode of sexual violence suffered by the mother during pregnancy. This revelation surfaced decades later, during therapeutic work with a psychologist, and brought to light the coexistence of two types of intrauterine memories: the positive, marked by the classical music played by the father, and the negative, shaped by the fear and tension caused by the abuse. The scientific section contextualises research indicating that, from the third trimester, the fetus is capable of recognising sounds, voices, and melodies, with lasting effects on memory, preferences, and neural connections. It also discusses how severe maternal stress can impact brain and emotional development, particularly in the third trimester - a period of intense neurological maturation. The hypothesis of fetal programming and epigenetic mechanisms is presented as an explanation for the enduring influence of such experiences. The text concludes with a provocative reflection: if a baby can learn melodies before birth, what happens when the first 'music' is the silence imposed by unspoken pain?

Keywords: Epigenetics, Fetal memory, Fetal trauma, Intergenerational sexual violence, Maternal stress, Prenatal trauma.

Introduction

The concept of fetal memory refers to the capacity of a fetus to store and process sensory information during the gestational period, with the possibility of retention after birth (Kisilevsky et al., 2003; Hepper, 1991). Studies indicate that, by the third trimester of pregnancy, the fetus is capable of recognising the maternal voice, distinguishing sound patterns, and developing musical and olfactory preferences (Schaal et al., 2000). Such findings have frequently been associated with positive experiences, such as exposure to music, reading, or affectionate stimuli.

However, the scientific literature remains scarce with regard to the recording of adverse experiences in the prenatal period, particularly in the context of intrafamilial sexual violence. Research on severe maternal stress points to impacts on the baby's neurological and emotional development, yet qualitative accounts that integrate traumatic experiences of both mother and child within the same temporal event are rarely included (Van den Bergh et al., 2017).

The present first-person account describes an experience of intergenerational sexual violence, occurring both during gestation and later in childhood, perpetrated by the same abuser. It also presents the coexistence of positive and negative memories recorded during the intrauterine period - including the affectionate recollection of classical music played by the father - alongside memories associated with fear and tension, possibly linked to the violence suffered by the mother at the same time.

This case study aims to contribute to the scientific debate on fetal memory and prenatal trauma, offering a personal perspective that highlights the complexity of intrauterine experiences and their potential influence on affective, cognitive, and psychological development throughout life.

Methodology

This study adopts the format of a first-person autobiographical account, interwoven with current scientific evidence. The experiences narrated were drawn from personal

memory and revised for clarity and narrative coherence. The literature review was conducted using academic databases, prioritising peer-reviewed articles published in the past 15 years, with an emphasis on studies addressing fetal memory, intrauterine sensory perception, maternal stress, and fetal programming.

First-Person Narrative

The Dream

I was in my mother's womb. In the dream, I knew this. I felt the warmth of the amniotic fluid surrounding me, like a gentle embrace. I remember the almost translucent scent of colours - greens, reds, and shades of orange that seemed to float around me. The sound touched my entire body, as though each vibration were also a caress. I heard voices.

Suddenly, something changed. A pain. A weight. A presence that did not belong in that space. An intrusion. In the dream, I felt a harrowing violence. In the dream, I knew I was in my mother's womb, and I felt as though I were being raped through her - that is exactly how I described it to my psychologist.

Dialogue and Interpretation in Therapy

I told my psychologist about the dream. She listened in silence and, before she could say anything, I added:

"I need to tell you something else. Please don't laugh, and don't think I'm lying or losing my mind... I have memories from when I was in my mother's womb. I remember a lot..."

A discreet look of surprise appeared on her face, and then she replied:

"Daniel, that's remarkable... you have fetal memory. There are few studies on this, but they do exist - and you're not mad. Based on the logic of this dream, which to me feels more like a memory from that intrauterine time, and considering some studies on

intergenerational abuse, it's possible that the person who abused you also did this to your mother."

Her words kept echoing in my mind. I wanted to be able to confirm it, but until that moment, it had not been possible.

Historical Context

In October 2019, I left Brazil. I was married and happy, and we moved to Ireland. Just a few months later, the world was struck by the COVID-19 pandemic. Life on the island changed radically: isolation, uncertainty, and an almost tangible atmosphere of tension. With no job, no prospects, and wrestling with internal conflicts, I began to feel increasingly lost.

In July 2020, I decided to end my marriage, and in September I moved to Portugal. There, I became involved in a highly toxic relationship. I cried every day. Alcohol and cigarettes became constant habits. From Ireland, my ex-wife, concerned for my wellbeing, suggested that I seek therapy.

That was how, in November 2020, I began seeing Brenda, my psychologist. Our sessions were weekly and online. When the crises worsened, we would arrange two sessions a week.

In our early conversations, I told her that my mother had left home when I was seven years old, in 1986. My maternal family took us in: during the day, we stayed at my maternal grandparents' house; in the evenings, my father would take us home. He worked all day and collected us after work. About a year and a half after she left, my mother reappeared a few times - not many, and I can't recall exactly how many - before disappearing again.

The last time I saw her in that period was striking. We were at my maternal grandparents' house when my father came home from work and found my mother there. What followed was an intense argument. It was the first - and perhaps the only - time I saw my father utter so many profanities and insults, especially inside the house that had

always welcomed him. I felt frightened and unsettled. He grabbed me by the arm, pulled me away from her, and took me home against my will.

Fast-forward to my therapy years: in 2021, I felt better and decided to stop the sessions - a huge mistake. I spent some months between Portugal and Ireland, but due to the abusive relationship in Portugal, I returned to Ireland in January 2022. In Portugal, I had gone through a very dark period, including two attempts to end my life in quick succession.

The toxic relationship came to an end, and in May 2022 I returned permanently to Ireland. Around that time, I faced two further acts of self-destruction. After the second, and with the support of my ex-wife, I made two decisions: to resume therapy and to reach out to my mother. I called my sister in Brazil and said:

“Find a way, track Mum down. I don’t want to live anymore, but before I go, I need to say goodbye to her.”

Talking with My Mum

Thirty-six years later, my mother came back into my life. During the first month, we talked for hours every day. On the third day, I asked her bluntly:

“Mum, have you ever been sexually assaulted?”

She was surprised by the question and replied:

“Can you keep a secret? I can keep secrets.”

I nodded, and taking a deep breath, she began to tell me. She said that, starting in her adolescence, around the age of fourteen, she suffered sexual abuse from an uncle, and that this continued for years, until shortly before she left home. These situations occurred when my father was away, and she never revealed to him what was happening.

In a moment of deep disclosure, she said there were times when she was visibly fragile, yet the people around her did not notice. She also recounted that some of these episodes took place during her pregnancy and, on at least one occasion, after I had been born and was in her arms. She tried to protect both herself and me, but could not prevent the violations from happening.

Fetal Memory on Two Sides

Upon hearing my mother's account, I realised that the dream I had had - in which I perceived myself still in the womb - might not have been merely a product of imagination, but possibly an extremely early memory, connected to what she experienced while carrying me. The maternal womb, in my case, was at once a place of affection and a space marked by threats.

My Dad's Classical Music (Positive Memory)

I had always heard that babies can hear and sense stimuli while still in the womb. In my case, I have memories that reinforce this idea. My father would place classical music records against my mother's belly so that I could 'listen'. He believed that this early experience could nurture my appreciation for art. Today, classical music is among my greatest preferences, and certain pieces evoke in me an immediate sense of calm, as though reconnecting me with that inner space of warmth and safety.

The Trauma During the Abuse (Negative Memory)

Yet, in the same space that enveloped me with soothing melodies, there also arose sensations of fear and tension - a reflection of the violence that my mother, and indirectly I, experienced during that time. These contrasts, between care and threat, marked the very beginning of my existence and left impressions that remain with me to this day.

The Scientific View

Auditory Perception and Fetal Memory

Research indicates that from the third trimester of pregnancy, the fetus is able to perceive external sounds, differentiate voices, and even recognise maternal speech, producing measurable changes in heart rate. There is evidence that, while still in the womb, the baby can distinguish between languages, identify melodies previously heard, and retain this memory after birth, influencing musical preferences and emotional responses (Arenillas-Alcón et al., 2022; Granier-Deferre et al., 2011; Gustafsson et al., 2022; Ortiz-Barajas, 2024; Partanen et al., 2013).

Prenatal musical exposure can, in addition to providing a calming effect, stimulate brain areas related to memory and emotions, promote the formation of neural connections, support the organisation of the auditory system and early cognitive development, and even induce lasting epigenetic modifications in gene expression (Marx & Nagy, 2015; Movalled et al., 2023; Yetkin et al., 2023).

Effects of Maternal Stress

Just as positive stimuli cross the uterine barrier, intense maternal stress also reaches the baby. The hormone cortisol, released in situations of tension, can cross the placenta and directly influence brain and emotional development. Elevated and prolonged levels of cortisol are associated with changes in brain areas responsible for emotional regulation and the fear response (Georgousopoulou et al., 2025; Howland et al., 2020; Sze & Brunton, 2024; Wu et al., 2024).

Longitudinal research indicates that high levels of stress during pregnancy are associated with an increased risk of cognitive difficulties, behavioural problems, and a predisposition to anxiety in childhood. The intensity of these effects may vary depending on the gestational period in which the stress occurred (Fleck et al., 2023; Li et al., 2025; Lund et al., 2025).

The Sensitivity of the Third Trimester

The third trimester is particularly critical for brain development. During this period, the fetal brain undergoes rapid expansion, with a significant increase in cortical volume and strengthening of connections between different regions. Neural networks become progressively more complex, allowing for the integration of sensory and emotional information. In addition, functional connectivity between cortical areas and limbic structures begins to consolidate, laying the foundations for cognitive and regulatory processes after birth. Positive and negative experiences lived by the mother at this stage - such as affectionate stimuli or periods of intense stress - can have a lasting influence on the child's brain architecture and emotional responses throughout life (Chen et al., 2024; Cook et al., 2023).

The Theory of Fetal Programming and Epigenetics

According to the fetal programming hypothesis, the conditions experienced before birth - such as the quality of maternal nutrition, exposure to sensory stimuli, and stress levels - exert a lasting influence on physical and mental health throughout life. This phenomenon is partly mediated by epigenetic mechanisms, which imprint biological marks of the intrauterine environment on the developing organism (Dieckmann & Czamara, 2024; Priviero, 2023; Stevenson et al., 2020).

Final Reflection

If a baby is capable of learning a melody even before being born, what happens when their first music is not made of notes and harmony, but of the heavy silence imposed by a pain no one dares to name? Perhaps that silence, too, becomes etched into the earliest memories, shaping internal rhythms that accompany a lifetime. And if the songs we inherit before we breathe are composed of both affection and fear, how do we rewrite that score over the course of our lives?

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